

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of ethane diol and butane-2,3-diol by tetrachloroaurate(III) in acetate buffer medium

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Abstract : The reductivities of ethane diol and butane-2,3-diol towards tetrachloroaurate(III) in acetate buffer medium have been studied. The reaction is of first order with respect to the oxidant but of complex order with respect to the substrate. The reaction is inhibited by both H^+ and Cl^- ions. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium diminishes the rate. Different thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. The reaction appears to involve a fast pre-equilibrium with the formation of an intermediate complex between $AuCl_4^-$ and diol and the complex then disproportionates in the rate limiting step to give the product and Au^I .

Keywords : Tetrachloroaurate(III), vicinal diol, acetate buffer, kinetics.

Gold(III) compounds were used earlier in the treatment of tuberculosis¹ while a few gold(III) complexes are recently found to have anti tumor activity². There are several reports of substitution reactions of gold(III)³⁻⁵. But kinetic studies in the reduction of Au^{III} by various inorganic⁶⁻¹⁵ as well as organic¹⁶⁻²¹ compounds have become increasingly interesting since Au^{III} may behave either as a one- or two-electron transfer oxidant just like Pt^{IV} or Ag^{III} . There are kinetic investigations for the oxidation of a few mono-ols²¹ by Au^{III} , however, oxidation of diols are lacking. The oxidation of two aliphatic vicinal diols by Au^{III} in an acetate buffer medium is studied over a wide range of experimental conditions. Since gold(III) chloride is partially hydrolysed^{3,22,23} at lower acidities ($[H^+] = (1.1-12.6) \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), and the reactions are too slow to be studied in a highly acidic medium ($[H^+] > 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), the reaction has been monitored in a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer medium where it occurs at a measurable rate.

Experimental

Reagents :

Ethane diol (ED) (A.R./S.R.L.) and butane-2,3-diol (B.D.) (mixture of meso and dl, E. Merck, Germany) were distilled just before use. Other reagents were of A.R. (S.R.L. or Merck-India) grades. A stock solution

of Au^{III} was prepared by dissolving chloroauric acid trihydrate (G.R./E. Merck, Germany) in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} HCl. The strength of the solution was determined by measurement of the absorbance of the solution (after proper dilution in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} HCl and 1 mol dm^{-3} NaCl) at the absorbance maximum¹⁶ (313 nm , $\epsilon = 4860 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $AuCl_4^-$. All the solutions were made in doubly distilled water.

Kinetic measurements :

In all the kinetic investigations, pseudo-first order conditions were maintained, where $[\text{substrate}] \gg [Au^{III}]$. The kinetic progress of the reaction was monitored by measurement of the absorbance at 400 nm for reasons as described earlier²¹. The diols are transparent at this wavelength. The kinetic measurements were made in a Systronics (India) visible spectrophotometer (model 166) using thermostatted cell of 1 cm path length. Generally, 16-18 experimental readings were taken in each run. Initially, there was a rapid decrease in absorbance (short-lived), which possibly indicated the formation of an intermediate complex. This was followed by a slow but steady decrease in absorbance, which would be accounted for by the redox reaction. From this second part of the reaction, the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was determined using a plot of $\log A$ ($A = \text{absorbance}$) versus time.

Product analysis :

The reaction mixture in each case under kinetic conditions was allowed to stand for 8 h and then distilled. The distillate was then subjected to the following tests.

For ethane diol the distillate was divided into three parts. To the first part an equal volume of 12 *N* H₂SO₄ was added followed by a pinch of chromotropic acid and warmed on a water bath for about 10 min when a pinkish violet colour appeared indicating the presence of methanal^{24a}. The second part of the distillate was treated with a small amount of gallic acid and a few drops of conc. H₂SO₄ and heated on a water bath for 15 min when a bluish green colouration was observed indicating the presence of methanal^{24b}. The third part of the distillate was treated with 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNP) solution in 4 (*N*) H₂SO₄ and heated on a water bath for about 30 min and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature when yellow crystals of DNP derivative of the product was precipitated. It was filtered, washed thoroughly and dried. The melting point of the derivative was found to be 165 °C^{25a} indicating the product to be HCHO.

For butane diol one part of the distillate was treated with an equal volume of 20% piperidine solution and a little of 5% sodium nitroprusside solution followed by addition of 2% solution of Na₂CO₃ when formation of a blue colour indicated the presence of ethanal in the product^{24c}. The second part of the distillate was treated with 2,4-D.N.P. solution similarly as in case of ED and the melting point of the orange crystals of the 2,4-D.N.P. derivative was found to be 145 °C^{25b} indicating the product to be CH₃CHO.

Polymerisation test :

The reaction mixture containing 30% (v/v) acrylonitrile was allowed to stand for 5 h. No polymerisation of acrylonitrile was observed. These observations showed that there was no free radical intermediate thus indicating the absence of involvement of a one-electron transfer process in the reduction of Au^{III} to Au^I.

Results and discussion

Effect of reactant concentration :

The oxidation of ED and BD by Au^{III} were studied at different initial [Au^{III}] ((2.16–4.32) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³),

keeping [substrate], [Cl⁻], pH and temperature constant at 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, 4.0 and 323 K respectively. The values of *k*_{obs} for the two diols were found to be almost constant viz. 1.14 (±0.07) × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ and 1.30 (±0.08) × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ respectively for the two diols ED and BD independent of the initial concentration of Au^{III}, indicating that the reaction is of first order in Au^{III}.

The influence of variation of diol concentration on the reaction rate was also studied at constant [Au^{III}], [Cl⁻] and pH of 2.16 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ and 4.0 respectively at four different temperatures. An increase in [diol] increased the value of *k*_{obs} at a particular temperature. A double reciprocal plot of *k*_{obs}⁻¹ versus [diol]⁻¹ at each temperature produced a straight line with a positive slope and a positive intercept (Fig. 1). Such plots would indicate the existence of a pre-equilibrium

Fig. 1. Plots of *k*_{obs}⁻¹ versus [diol]⁻¹ for ethane and butane diol at four different temperatures : [Au^{III}] = 2.16 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Cl⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.0; (□, ■) 308 K, (○, ●) 313 K, (△, ▲) 318 K, (▽, ▼) 323 K.

involving the oxidant and the diol to form an intermediate complex. From the intercepts and slopes of these lines, the values of *k*_d and *K* [vide eq. (12)] for the two diols at four different temperatures were evaluated (Table 1).

Effect of ionic strength :

The effect of changing ionic strength on the pseudo-first order constant was studied by the addition of sodium perchlorate keeping [Au^{III}], [ED], pH and temperature constant at 2.16 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, 4.0 and 308 K respectively. The value of *k*_{obs} was found to decrease initially to a small extent and then increased again almost to the initial value for a change of ionic strength from 0.05 to 0.25 (Table 2).

Table 1. Values of k_d and K and thermodynamic parameters for the two diols at four different temperatures

Temp. (K)	$10^4 k_d$ (ED) (s^{-1})	$10^5 K$ (ED) ($mol\ dm^{-3}$)	$10^4 k_d$ (BD) (s^{-1})	$10^5 K$ (BD) ($mol\ dm^{-3}$)
308	0.676	9.75	0.586	1.29
313	0.909	13.13	0.653	2.11
318	1.090	17.61	0.733	2.60
323	1.282	23.27	0.777	3.63
ΔH° ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)		45.2	54.7	
ΔH^\ddagger ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)		32.3	14.5	
ΔS° ($JK^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$)		147	103	
ΔS^\ddagger ($JK^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$)		-220	-279	

Table 2. Effect of variation of ionic strength on the pseudo-first order rate constant

$[Au^{III}] = 2.16 \times 10^{-3}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $[ED] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $[Cl^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $pH = 4.00$, $temp. = 308\ K$

$10^2 [NaClO_4]$ ($mol\ dm^{-3}$)	μ ($mol\ dm^{-3}$)	$10^5 k_{obs}$ (s^{-1})
0.0	0.05	5.75
2.0	0.07	4.99
5.0	0.10	5.18
10.0	0.15	5.75
15.0	0.20	5.68
20.0	0.25	5.54

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration :

The effect of changing $[H^+]$ on the pseudo-first order rate constant was studied by changing the pH of the buffer solution from 3.16 to 4.55 at a constant $[Au^{III}] = 2.16 \times 10^{-3}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ and $[ED] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$. No attempt was made to keep the ionic strength constant since the reaction was carried out in a buffer medium. The rate has been found to be inhibited by an increase of $[H^+]$. A plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[H^+]$ was found to be linear (Fig. 2) with positive slope and positive intercept. From the intercept and slope of the linear plot the value of k_d and K for ED at 308 K were evaluated to be $0.800 \times 10^{-4}\ s^{-1}$ and $3.85 \times 10^{-5}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ respectively. Since the ionic strength could not be maintained constant, it is quite plausible that the changed ionic strength may have a small influence on the rate constant. Moreover, at higher pH values, other Au^{III} species, viz. $AuCl_3(H_2O)$ and $AuCl_3(OH)^-$ may become involved in the oxidation processes, thereby making the reaction faster as well as much more complicated. These two facts possibly account for the slight deviation of the values of k_d and K from those obtained from substrate effect.

Fig. 2. Plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[H^+]$ for the oxidation of ethane diol : $[Au^{III}] = 2.16 \times 10^{-3}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $[Cl^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $[ED] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $temp. = 308\ K$.

Effect of chloride ion concentration :

The influence of changing $[Cl^-]$ on the value of k_{obs} was studied by the addition of NaCl, keeping $[Au^{III}]$, $[ED]$, pH and temperature constant at $2.16 \times 10^{-3}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $5 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, 4.0 and 308 K respectively. Chloride ion was found to have an inhibiting effect on the reaction rate. A plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[Cl^-]$ was again linear (Fig. 3) and from the intercept and slope of the straight line, the values of k_d and K were evaluated to be $0.714 \times 10^{-4}\ s^{-1}$ and $5.21 \times 10^{-5}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ respectively at 308 K. The value of k_d tallies very well with that obtained from substrate effect (Table 1). The slight discrepancy in the value of K (as obtained from the substrate

Fig. 3. Plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[Cl^-]$ for the oxidation of ethane diol : $[Au^{III}] = 2.16 \times 10^{-3}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $[ED] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}\ mol\ dm^{-3}$, $pH = 4.0$, $temp. = 308\ K$.

effect) may be accounted for by the change of ionic strength during the investigation.

The effect of changing the dielectric constant of the medium on the reaction rate was studied by the addition of dioxane keeping $[Au^{III}]$, $[ED]$, pH and temperature constant at $2.16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 4.0 and 308 K respectively. The value of k_{obs} was observed to decrease with an increase in the percentage of dioxane in the medium (Table 3). This indicates that k_{obs} decreases with a decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium.

Table 3. Effect of variation of solvent composition on the pseudo-first order rate constant

$[Au^{III}] = 2.16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[ED] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.00, temp. = 308 K and $[Cl^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$						
% Dioxane (v/v)	0.00	2.0	5.0	10.0	15.0	20.0
$10^5 k_{obs} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	5.60	4.90	3.77	3.55	3.18	3.10

The reaction rates were studied at four different temperatures, keeping $[Au^{III}]$, pH and $[Cl^-]$ constant but varying the substrate concentrations. The values of k_d and K at different temperatures were evaluated from the plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[diol]^{-1}$ for the two diols. The plot of $\log(k_d/T)$ versus $1/T$ was linear in each case and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) for the disproportionation step [eq. (9)] were calculated (Table 4) using Eyring equation.

$$\log(k_d/T) = [\log(k_B/h) + (\Delta S^\ddagger/2.303R)] - (\Delta H^\ddagger/2.303RT) \quad (3)$$

Again the plots of $\log K$ versus $1/T$ for the two diols were also linear and the values of ΔH° associated with the complex formation for all the three diols were evaluated from these plots followed by the estimation of ΔS° (Table 1) from the relation,

$$\log K = [\Delta S^\circ - (\Delta H^\circ/T)]/2.303R \quad (4)$$

The following equilibria are known to exist^{5,6} in a dilute solution of tetrachloroauric(III) acid :

where $K_1 = 1.0$, $K_2 = 9.5 \times 10^{-6}$ and $K_3 = 0.25$ at 298

K. Consequently, four different species, viz. $HAuCl_4$, $AuCl_4^-$, $AuCl_3(H_2O)$ and $AuCl_3(OH)^-$ may exist in a solution of chloroauric acid. However, since most of the reactions were carried out at an $[H^+] \sim 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, it is evident that $AuCl_4^-$ is the predominant Au^{III} species over $HAuCl_4$ acting as the oxidant in the present system. Further in all the reactions, $[Cl^-] \geq 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and from the known value of K_2 it is clear that the equilibrium (6) lies far towards left and $[AuCl_4^-] \gg [AuCl_3(H_2O)]$. Also at this low acidity of the medium the protonation of the diol is unlikely. Therefore, a plausible mechanism is that $AuCl_4^-$ oxidizes the neutral molecules of diol. The reaction is inhibited by both H^+ and Cl^- ions and linear double reciprocal plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[diol]^{-1}$ indicates the formation of an intermediate complex. Hence, it is proposed that the reaction between $AuCl_4^-$ and diol involves a pre-equilibrium [eq. (8)] with the formation of an intermediate complex (X) along with the release of H^+ and Cl^- ions, followed by the disproportionation of the complex in the rate determining step to yield the corresponding aldehydes and gold(I).

Such type of intermediate complexes have already been found in the reduction of chloroaurate(III) by glycine¹⁹ and α -hydroxy acids²⁰. Since the diol is present in a large excess compared to Au^{III} , further oxidation of the product aldehyde (which is produced in a very small amount) is unlikely although it cannot be totally ruled out.

Based on the above mechanistic steps, the rate of disappearance of Au^{III} may be expressed as

$$\frac{-d[Au^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{k_d K [Au^{III}] [diol]}{K [diol] + [H^+][Cl^-]} \quad (10)$$

and the pseudo-first order rate constant,

$$\begin{aligned} k_{obs} &= - \frac{1}{[Au^{III}]} \frac{d[Au^{III}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k_d K [diol]}{K [diol] + [H^+][Cl^-]} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The equation may be rearranged as,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_d} + \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{k_d K} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{diol}]} \quad (12)$$

Thus at constant $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and at a specified temperature a plot k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{diol}]^{-1}$ was expected to be a straight line with a positive slope and positive intercept and this has been observed for each of the two diols. Again at constant $[\text{ED}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and temperature a plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is linear as expected from eq. (10) and the values of k_d and K are close to the values of k_d and K obtained from substrate effect at that temperature. Eq. (10) also demands a linear plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{H}^+]$ at constant $[\text{diol}]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and temperature. Such a linear plot was obtained with ED. However, the values of k_d and K evaluated from such plot are found to deviate slightly from those obtained from substrate effect. This discrepancy may be accounted for by the following two facts : (a) Since in these studies, ionic strength could not be maintained constant, it was quite plausible that the changed ionic strength might have a small influence on the rate constant and (b) at higher pH, other Au^{III} species, viz. $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ might participate in the oxidation processes, thereby making the reaction faster as well as much more complicated. It has already been found in a number of investigations^{4,13} that $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ are more reactive than AuCl_4^- . Thus a higher value of k_{obs} at higher pH region will ultimately lead to a smaller value of K as obtained in the present experiment.

In the stable conformation of ED, two -OH groups are in gauche form²⁶. Thus the formation of the cyclic intermediate complex (Scheme 1) and its decomposition to the product may be visualized as

Scheme 1

In the case of BD (both meso- and dl-forms) also, the gauche conformers predominate²⁶ owing to intramolecular H-bonding between the two -OH groups.

Scheme 2

The two gauche conformers of the meso form are equally populated. But in case of both the optically active isomers, the gauche conformers with two methyl groups anti to each other will predominate over the other. But irrespective of whether it is optically active or inactive form, it is evident from the Scheme 2 that formation of the cyclic intermediate complex from the hydrogen bonded structure decreases the torsion angle between the two methyl groups (in both the meso forms and one active form) or between the methyl and the -OH groups (in case of active form as shown in the Scheme 2) thereby increasing the steric interaction. This is the reason why the enthalpy of complex formation (ΔH°) is slightly higher for BD than ED and the value of K decreases in the order $K_{(\text{ED})} > K_{(\text{BD})}$. Further, since BD exists in a mixture of different enantiomeric as well as conformational isomers, statistically the initial entropy of the reactant (BD) is expected to be higher as compared to ED which exists predominantly as a single form. This may lead to a lesser change in entropy (ΔS°) for BD than ED.

During the slow step, decomposition will be easier as the steric crowding increases in the complex from ED to BD, because there will be release of steric strain as the relevant C-C bond breaks down. This is supported by the decrease of ΔH^\ddagger from ED to BD. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger is accounted for by the fact that as the intermediate complex decomposes in the rate determining step, several charged species are produced which indicates that the transition state for this step (9) will be much polar leading to an increase in electrostriction which results in a negative entropy of activation. This is reflected in the observation that the reaction rate is retarded by an increase in the proportion of dioxane in the medium, as the formation of the more polar transition state is likely to be disfavored by a decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium. Thus all the kinetic evidences, the product analyses and absence of polymerization in presence of acrylonitrile justify the proposed mechanism in which the vicinal aliphatic diols are oxidized by Au^{III} in a two-electron

transfer process via an intermediate cyclic complex formation.

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